

PERIODATES OF QUADRIVALENT METALS.

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Periodates of a few quadrivalent metals have been prepared and their percentage composition determined.

Little work on the periodates of quadrivalent metals has been done. Cleve (*Bull. soc. chim.*, 1875, ii, 21, 115) has mentioned that periodic acid yields in the solution of a thorium salt, a bulky amorphous precipitate of variable composition. No other periodate of tetravalent metal has been described.

The present investigation was, therefore, undertaken with a view to preparing the periodates of certain tetravalent metals and studying their properties.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Ceric Paraperiodate.—Pure ceric ammonium nitrate was dissolved in dilute nitric acid and on adding to it trisodium paraperiodate ($\text{Na}_3\text{H}_2\text{IO}_6$), dissolved in dilute nitric acid, a shining yellow precipitate was obtained. It was filtered, washed with dilute nitric acid and finally with water and dried in a vacuum desiccator over concentrated sulphuric acid and solid caustic soda. The dry salt formed shining yellow crystals. It liberated iodine when strongly heated. Iodine was estimated volumetrically and cerium as ceric oxide. (Found : I, 33'25 ; Ce 36'33. CeHIO_6 , H_2O requires I, 33'22 ; Ce, 36'67 per cent).

Thorium Paraperiodate.—sodium paraperiodate, dissolved in dilute nitric acid, was added in excess to pure thorium nitrate, dissolved in dilute nitric acid. There was no immediate precipitation. The mixture was placed on the water-bath. A white gelatinous precipitate separated after a long time. When the precipitation was complete, it was filtered, washed with dilute nitric acid and finally with water, and dried in a vacuum desiccator. It formed transparent crystals insoluble in water and decomposed on heating to 600° . (Found : I, 24'08 ; Th, 41'9. ThHIO_6 , $5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires I, 23'27 ; Th, 42'51 per cent).

Titanium Periodate.—Ammonium titanifluoride was heated strongly in a basin with excess of concentrated sulphuric acid, digested with water for a long time and filtered. Excess of ammonium hydroxide was added to the filtrate, when white gelatinous titanium hydroxide, $\text{Ti}(\text{OH})_4$, was precipitated. It was filtered and washed free of ammonia. Titanium

hydroxide was dissolved in dilute nitric acid and added to a solution of $\text{Na}_2\text{H}_2\text{IO}_6$ in dilute nitric acid. At first there was no precipitate. The liquid was concentrated on the water-bath, when a white powdery precipitate was obtained. It was filtered, washed with dilute nitric acid and then with water. It formed opaque crystals. (Found : I, 28'31 ; Ti, 35'65. $7\text{TiO}_2, \text{I}_2\text{O}_7$ requires I, 27'45 ; Ti, 35'20 per cent).

Stannic Periodate.—Stannic chloride was poured into a large excess of ammonium hydroxide, when the white precipitate of stannic hydroxide was precipitated. It was filtered, washed free of chloride, dissolved in dilute nitric acid and added to a nitric acid solution of trisodium para-periodate. At first there was no precipitate but after a few minutes there was a slight turbidity. On heating it on the water-bath for about fifteen minutes copious white precipitate was formed. It was filtered, washed with dilute nitric acid and then with water and dried over concentrated sulphuric acid in a vacuum desiccator. It formed opaque crystals. (Found : I, 28'19 ; Sn, 49'64. $4\text{SnO}_2, \text{I}_2\text{O}_7$ requires I, 26'6 ; Sn, 49'0 per cent).

Zirconium Periodate.—Zirconium oxide was heated strongly with concentrated sulphuric acid for a long time. The mass was digested with water and filtered. The zirconium sulphate, in the filtrate was treated with excess of ammonium hydroxide, when a white gelatinous precipitate of zirconium hydroxide was precipitated, which was dissolved in dilute nitric acid and added to a solution of $\text{Na}_2\text{H}_2\text{IO}_6$ in dilute nitric acid when immediate white precipitate was formed ; it was kept on the water-bath for a long time for complete precipitation. It was filtered through a Bucher funnel, washed with dilute nitric acid and finally with water and dried in a vacuum desiccator over concentrated sulphuric acid and solid caustic soda. (Found : I, 26'1 ; Zr, 24'6. $3\text{ZrO}_2, \text{I}_2\text{O}_7, 17\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires I, 24'4 ; Zr, 26'2 per cent).

All the compounds are quite stable and are not affected by boiling water. When strongly heated they all decompose with the liberation of iodine and oxygen.

Work on trivalent, pentavalent and other tetravalent metals are in progress. The author's sincere thanks are due to Prof. P. Ray for kindly suggesting this piece of work and for all the facilities in his laboratory.